

A comprehensive comparison of Two-Fluid Model, Discrete Element Method and experiments for the simulation of single- and multiple-spout fluidized beds

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A comparison between TFM, CFD-DEM, and experiments was performed.
- A new modification to $\mu(I)$ -rheology to consider rolling friction in TFM was proposed.
- The effect of two different frictional solids stresses was examined in TFM.
- Four Different drag models were tested in TFM and CFD-DEM.
- Using proper TFM closures improves the comparisons with CFD-DEM and experiments.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

We employ a two-fluid model (TFM) as well as a computational fluid dynamics coupled to discrete element method (CFD-DEM) approach to study the time averaged hydrodynamics of single- and multiple-spout fluidized beds. Simulations are validated against the experimental data of (van Buijtenen et al., Numerical and experimental study on multiple-spout fluidized beds, Chemical Engineering Science 66 (2011) 2368–2376) with four different interphase drag correlations. The kinetic theory of granular flow used for solving the motion of the solid phase in TFM, includes realistic particle–wall boundary conditions for momentum transfer and the flux of pseudo-thermal energy. Frictional stresses in TFM are modelled based on a $\mu(I)$ -rheology. We propose a new ad hoc modification of the $\mu(I)$ -rheology to account for the effect of rolling friction in TFM. In contrast, in CFD-DEM rolling friction is accounted by an additional torque. Our results show that there is a good agreement between both approaches with respect to time averaged volume fraction, solids velocities, solids fluxes and granular temperature.

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1. Introduction

Spout fluidized beds that combine the favorable properties of both fluidized and spouted beds, were proposed by Chatterjee

(Chatterjee, 1970). This combination enhances particle circulation and mixing as well as a lower total flow rate is needed to fluidize particles in these beds compared to fluidized and spouted beds (Sutkar et al., 2013). In "single-spout fluidized beds," high velocity gas enters the bed through a nozzle, while lower velocity background gas is introduced from a distributor around the nozzle. In case of more than one high velocity gas nozzle, the bed is called "multiple-spout fluidized bed." Due to the mentioned advantages, the spout fluidized beds have been employed in various processes, including gasification, chemical looping combustion, pyrolysis, and catalytic oxidation (Albina, 2006; Shen et al., 2010; Thamavithya and Dutta, 2008; Xie et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2019).

In the past decades, two main modelling approaches have been used to analyse hydrodynamics of spout fluidized beds. On the one hand, the Eulerian-Eulerian approach (e.g. two-fluid model, TFM), where both phases are treated as interpenetrating continua, is preferably used for larger scales. On the other hand, the Eulerian-Lagrangian approach (e.g. computational fluid dynamics coupled with discrete element method, CFD-DEM), where the gas phase is considered as continuous phase and the particles are tracked individually, is commonly used for more detailed descriptions. The TFM approach requires less computational time than CFD-DEM approach, but the accuracy of TFM simulations is strongly connected to the used constitutive closures of particle-particle interactions and particle-wall collisions. However, particle-particle and particle-wall collisions can be explicitly taken into account in CFD-DEM approach using physical models such as hard sphere or soft sphere models. Besides, particles are not perfectly spherical in experiments, and the non-sphericity of the particles could significantly affect results; therefore, incorporating the effect of particle non-sphericity in modelling in terms of the rolling friction is essential (Goniva et al., 2012; Ai et al., 2011). Furthermore, interphase drag force plays an imperative role in capturing the gas-solid interactions in TFM and CFD-DEM modelling of gas-solid systems and extensive researches about its effect on simulations of gas-solids systems justifies this matter (Li et al., 2017; Bian et al., 2020; Marchelli et al., 2020; Loha et al., 2012; Du et al., 2006). A direct comparison of TFM and CFD-DEM approaches for simulations of the spout fluidized beds can shed light on their advantages and limitations. In addition, the validity of the derived constitutive closures for particle-particle interactions and particle-wall boundary conditions in TFM approach can be examined in modelling of the spout fluidized beds. There are extensive studies in the literature on the modelling of the spout fluidized beds with either CFD-DEM (Jajcevic et al., 2013; Link et al., 2005; Link et al., 2007; Link et al., 2008; Sutkar et al., 2013; van Buijtenen et al., 2009; Buijtenen et al., 2012; van Buijtenen et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2019; Yue et al., 2019; Yue et al., 2021) or TFM (Zhao et al., 2021; Schneiderbauer et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2014; Wu et al., yyy; Zhao et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2022) approaches. For instance, Link et al. (Link et al., 2005) investigated the CFD-DEM simulations of the single-spout fluidized beds in different flow regimes, and van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) studied different

flow regimes in the multiple-spout fluidized beds via experiments and CFD-DEM simulations. Additionally, Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) validated their TFM simulations with derived constitutive closures for kinetic-collisional and frictional solids stresses along with a realistic particle-wall boundary condition against the spout fluidized bed experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). However, there are a few comparative studies between TFM and CFD-DEM in the literature for the spout fluidized beds; Table 1 summarises these studies. Guo et al. (Guo et al., 2021) used the interphase drag model of Gidaspow (Gidaspow, 1994) as the best fit for both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches and compared the results in terms of instantaneous bed height experimental data. Also, Chen et al. (Chen et al., 2019) used different interphase drag models for TFM and CFD-DEM approaches, as denoted in the Table 1. Neither approach was validated against experiments in their study and both approaches were compared by instantaneous profiles of bed height, solids volume fraction, and axial particle velocity. Similarly, Almohammed et al. (Almohammed et al., 2014) examined three different interphase drag correlations for TFM simulations and chose Syamlal O'Brien (Syamlal and O'Brien, 1987) as the proper drag model, and applied the interphase drag model of Koch and Hill (Hill et al., 2001) for CFD-DEM simulations, as shown in Table 1. The instantaneous bed height and equivalent bubble diameter were validated using both approaches. All of these studies employed instantaneous comparisons between two approaches, and no information was provided regarding time averaged spout fluidized bed hydrodynamics. Further, none of these studies considered the background velocity in their studied spout fluidized bed which is the key difference between the spout fluidized beds and spouted beds that affects the bed's flow regime (Link et al., 2005; van Buijtenen et al., 2011). In spout fluidized beds, particle-particle and particle-wall interactions are dominated by kinetic-collisional solids stresses in the spout and fountain regions. In the annulus region where solids volume fraction is high and particles are in close contacts, frictional solids stresses are dominant. Due to discrete nature of the CFD-DEM method, it can fully resolve the contacts in all regions, however in the TFM approach, closures are needed to sufficiently consider these interactions. In the commonly used TFM approach for modelling of the spout fluidized beds (Guo et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2019; Almohammed et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2014; Wu et al., yyy; Zhao et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2022), interstitial fluid effect on the kinetic-collisional solids stresses and pseudo-thermal energy flux has been ignored while studies of Wartha et al. (Wartha et al., 2022), Agrawal et al. (Agrawal et al., 2001) and Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) reveal its importance. Furthermore, conventional frictional solids stresses models based on Coulomb's law (Schaeffer, 1987; Syamlal et al., 1993; Johnson and Jackson, 1987; Johnson et al., 1990; Srivastava and Sundaresan, 2003; Benyahia, 2008) manifest order-zero dependence on the rate of deformation in the quasi-static granular regime and are suitable just for dense regimes (Van Wachem et al., 2001). The mostly used

Table 1
Previous studies comparing TFM and CFD-DEM in the spout fluidized beds.

Author	Interphase drag models	Bed type
Guo et al. (2021) (Guo et al., 2021)	Gidaspow (Gidaspow, 1994) (TFM and CFD-DEM), Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007), Koch and Hill (Hill et al., 2001) and Syamlal O'Brien (Syamlal and O'Brien, 1987)	Single-spout
Chen et al. (2019) (Chen et al., 2019)	Syamlal O'Brien (Syamlal and O'Brien, 1987) (TFM) and DeFelice (Di Felice, 1994) (CFD-DEM)	Multiple-spout
Almohammed et al. (2014) (Almohammed et al., 2014)	Gidaspow (Gidaspow, 1994), Wen and Yu (Wen, 1966), Syamlal O'Brien (Syamlal and O'Brien, 1987) (TFM) and Koch and Hill (Hill et al., 2001) (CFD-DEM)	Single-spout

closures of frictional solids stresses in the literature (Zhao et al., 2021; Guo et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2022) such as Johnson and Jackson (Johnson and Jackson, 1987), Srivastava and Sundaresan (Srivastava and Sundaresan, 2003) and Syamlal et al. (Syamlal et al., 1993) strongly depend on empirical parameter of minimum solids volume fraction, α_s^{min} (the point, where frictional stresses become non-negligible), and are monotonically increasing functions with increasing solids volume fraction. In addition, particle-wall impacts in these TFM simulations are resolved with Johnson and Jackson (Johnson and Jackson, 1987) boundary condition. This boundary condition considers momentum transfer and flux of pseudo-thermal energy of sliding and non-sliding collisional granular regimes by non-measurable specular coefficient; sliding collisional regime requires lower specular coefficient and higher specular coefficient should be used in non-sliding collisional regime. However, in the spout fluidized beds both sliding and non-sliding regimes are existing simultaneously, in the spout region sliding regime is dominant while in the annulus region non-sliding regime occurs. Therefore it is not feasible to realistically resolve the collisions in the spout fluidized beds via Johnson and Jackson (Johnson and Jackson, 1987) boundary condition using specular coefficient. Finally, the effect of particle non-sphericity is not considered in these simulations. In this paper, a comprehensive study between TFM, CFD-DEM and experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the single-, double- and triple-spout fluidized beds is carried out to shed light on the advantages and disadvantages of the TFM and CFD-DEM approaches in predicting the time averaged hydrodynamics of these beds. In Section 2.1, the governing equations of the CFD-DEM approach with considering rolling friction are explained. Section 2.2 covers the governing equations of the TFM approach and kinetic-collisional solids stresses with considering the effect of interstitial fluid and surrounding walls. Furthermore, it covers frictional solids stresses closures based on inertial number dependent rheology ($\mu(I)$ -rheology) and dilation laws. In addition, a realistic particle-wall boundary condition based on sliding and non-sliding collisional regimes, for momentum transfer and the flux of pseudo-thermal energy is presented. Furthermore, a new ad hoc modification to $\mu(I)$ -rheology for taking into account the influence of the rolling friction on the frictional solids stresses is discussed. Interphase drag force correlations derived from DNS and experiments are presented in Section 2.3. In Section 3 implementation details and simulation parameters are discussed. In Sections 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 first TFM and CFD-DEM validations against the experiments are provided and then a comprehensive comparison between CFD-DEM (as reference data) and TFM approaches in terms of the time averaged vertical solids velocities profiles, solids volume fraction profiles, solids axial flux and granular temperature profiles in the single-, double- and triple-spout fluidized beds is presented. It is shown that our applied TFM approach shows good agreement with experiments and CFD-DEM results.

2. Numerical approaches

2.1. CFD-DEM

In this paper, a discrete element method (DEM) introduced by Cundall and Strack (Cundall and Strack, 1979) for the solid phase and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) for fluid phase are applied. Due to limitations of "resolved CFD-DEM" in modelling a high number of particles and large computational domains, "unresolved CFD-DEM" approach, where computational cells are larger than particle diameter are used. Although this approach neglects flow around particles, particles are fully resolved in the DEM section and the computational time is considerably lower; thus "unre-

solved CFD-DEM" approach is preferable in modelling of large-scale systems of particle-laden flows (Golshan et al., 2017; Esgandari et al., 2021).

2.1.1. Fluid phase governing equations

As proposed by Anderson and Jackson (Anderson and Jackson, 1967), in the presence of solid phase, mass and momentum equations are modified to take into account fluid volume fraction, α_f . The modified equations can be written as

$$\frac{\partial(\alpha_f \rho_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \alpha_f \boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \mathbf{F}_{drag} + \alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{g} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_f is the fluid density, \mathbf{u}_f is the fluid velocity and α_f is fluid volume fraction, p is the pressure, \mathbf{g} represents the gravitational force and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ the deviatoric stress tensor, e.g. of Newtonian form

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_f = 2\mu_f \left(\frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}_f + \nabla \mathbf{u}_f^T) - \frac{1}{3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{I} \right) \quad (3)$$

The term \mathbf{F}_{drag} denotes the solids-fluid momentum exchange and can be described as

$$\mathbf{F}_{drag} = \frac{1}{\Delta V_c} \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{DEM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{s,i}) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{u}_s , n , ΔV_c and β_{DEM} are the solids translational velocity, number of particles in the computational cell, volume of the cell and interphase drag force coefficient in CFD-DEM approach.

2.1.2. Solid phase governing equations

The soft-sphere DEM approach which tracks trajectories of every individual particle by solving Newton's equation of motion is used. The equations of translational and rotational motion of particle i can be expressed as

$$m_i \dot{\mathbf{u}}_{s,i} = \sum_{i \neq j} \mathbf{F}_i^{(contact)} + \mathbf{F}_i^{(f-s)} + \mathbf{F}_i^{(ext)} \quad (5)$$

$$I_i \dot{\omega}_i = \mathbf{T}_i \quad (6)$$

where m_i , $\mathbf{u}_{s,i}$, I_i and ω_i are the particle mass, the particle translational velocity, the particle moment of inertia and the particle rotational velocity, respectively. In addition, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(contact)}$ are particle-particle interaction of surrounding particles j on particle i and particle-wall interactions described by non-linear Hertzian spring dashpot model (Tsuji et al., 1993) which normal and tangential contact forces are presented in Table 2. It should be mentioned that in case of using low restitution coefficient value, there might be an attractive normal contact force between particles and wall, therefore we bounded the normal contact force by zero in our simulations. Moreover, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(ext)}$ are external forces acting on the particle i which in this paper, gravitational force $\mathbf{F}_i^{(g)} = m_i \mathbf{g}$ is the only external force and solids-fluid interaction force, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(f-s)}$, can be defined as (see Table 3)

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{(f-s)} = \mathbf{F}_{drag,i} + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla p,i} + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f,i} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{drag,i} = \beta_{DEM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_i)$ is the interphase drag force on the particle, $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla p,i} = -V_p \nabla p$ is the pressure gradient force and $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f,i} = -V_p \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ the viscous force originated from deviatoric stress tensor where V_p is the particle volume. The fluid phase properties have been linearly interpolated at the particle position. The Basset

Table 2
Particle contact forces (Golshan et al., 2020).

Normal contact force exerted on particles:
 $\mathbf{F}^{(n)} = -(k_n \delta_n \mathbf{n} + \gamma_n \dot{\delta}_n)$

Tangential contact force exerted on particles:
 $\mathbf{F}^{(t)} = \begin{cases} -(k_t \delta_t \mathbf{t} + \gamma_t \dot{\delta}_t) & |\mathbf{F}^{(t)}| < \mu_s |\mathbf{F}^{(n)}| \\ -\mathbf{t} \mu_s |\mathbf{F}^{(n)}| & |\mathbf{F}^{(t)}| \geq \mu_s |\mathbf{F}^{(n)}| \end{cases}$

Particle normal stiffness coefficient:
 $k_n = \frac{4}{3} E^* \sqrt{R^* \delta_{n,ij}}$

Particle normal damping coefficient:
 $\gamma_n = -\beta \sqrt{5m^* k_n}$, $\beta = \frac{\ln(\epsilon)}{\sqrt{\ln^2(\epsilon) + \pi^2}}$

Particle tangential stiffness coefficient:
 $k_t = 8G^* \sqrt{R^* \delta_{n,ij}}$

Particle tangential damping coefficient:
 $\gamma_t = -\beta \sqrt{\frac{10}{3} m^* k_t}$

Normal unit vector along the line of centers of particle i and j:
 $\mathbf{n} \equiv \frac{\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|}$

Tangential unit vector along the line of centers of particle i and j:
 $\mathbf{t} \equiv \frac{\mathbf{u}_i}{|\mathbf{u}_i|}$

Effective Young's modulus:
 $E^* = \left(\frac{1-\nu_i^2}{E_i} + \frac{1-\nu_j^2}{E_j} \right)^{-1}$

Effective shear modulus:
 $G^* = \left(\frac{2-\nu_i}{G_i} + \frac{2-\nu_j}{G_j} \right)^{-1}$

Effective particle radius:
 $R^* = \left(\frac{1}{R_i} + \frac{1}{R_j} \right)^{-1}$

Effective particle mass:
 $m^* = \left(\frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{m_j} \right)^{-1}$

Table 3
Constitutive relations of TFM momentum equation (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012; Agrawal et al., 2001; Dabbagh and Schneiderbauer, 2021).

Pseudo-thermal energy equation:
 $\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_s \rho_s \Theta) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s \Theta) \right) = -\mathbf{S}_s^{\text{kc}} : \nabla \mathbf{u}_s - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + \Gamma_s - J_\nu - \gamma_\Theta$ (13)

Kinetic-collisional solids stress tensor:
 $\mathbf{S}_s^{\text{kc}} = (p_s^{\text{kc}} - \lambda_s^{\text{kc}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}_s)) \mathbf{I} - 2\mu_s^{\text{kc}} \text{dev} \mathbf{D}_s$, $\mathbf{D}_s = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}_s + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_s)^T)$, $\text{dev} \mathbf{D}_s = \mathbf{D}_s - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}_s) \mathbf{I}$ (14)

Solids viscosity:
 $\mu_s^{\text{kc}} = \frac{(2+\alpha')}{3} \left\{ \frac{\mu^*}{g_0 \eta_s (2-\eta_s)} \left(\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\alpha'}} + \frac{8}{5} \alpha_s \eta_s g_0 \right) \left(1 + \frac{8}{5} \eta_s (3\eta_s - 2) \alpha_s g_0 \right) + \frac{3}{5} \eta_s \mu_b \right\}$ (15)

$\mu^* = \frac{\mu}{1 + \frac{2\beta_{TFM} \mu}{(\alpha_s \rho_s)^2 g_0 \Theta}}$, $\mu = \frac{5\rho_s d_s \sqrt{\pi \Theta}}{96}$, $\mu_b = \frac{256\mu \alpha_s^2 g_0}{5\pi}$, $\alpha' = \frac{8}{5}$, $\eta_s = \frac{1}{2} (1 + e_{p-p})$, (16)

$l_s = \frac{d_s}{6\sqrt{2} g_0 \alpha_s}$.

Radial distribution function:
 $g_0 = \frac{1}{1 - \min(\alpha_s, \alpha_s^{\text{min}}) / \alpha_s^{\text{max}}}$ (17)

Pseudo-thermal energy (PTE) flux vector \mathbf{q} , rate of dissipation of PTE γ_Θ , rate of dissipation of PTE by viscous damping J_ν and rate of production of PTE by gas-particle slip Γ_s :
 $\mathbf{q} = -\frac{\kappa^*}{g_0} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\alpha'}} + \frac{12}{5} \eta_s \alpha_s g_0 \right) + \left(1 + \frac{12}{5} \eta_s^2 (4\eta_s - 3) \alpha_s g_0 \right) + \frac{64}{25\pi} (41 - 33\eta_s) \eta_s^2 \alpha_s^2 g_0^2 \right\} \nabla \Theta$, (18)

$\gamma_\Theta = \frac{48}{\sqrt{\pi}} \eta_s (1 - \eta_s) \frac{\rho_s \alpha_s^2}{d_s} g_0 \Theta^{3/2}$, $\kappa^* = \frac{\kappa}{1 + \frac{6\beta_{TFM} \kappa}{(\alpha_s \rho_s)^2 g_0 \Theta}}$, $\kappa = \frac{75\rho_s d_s \sqrt{\pi \Theta}}{48\eta_s (41 - 33\eta_s)}$, (19)

$\Gamma_s = \frac{d_s \beta_{TFM}^2 \|\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s\|^2}{4\alpha_s g_0 \rho_s \sqrt{\pi \Theta}}$, $J_\nu = 3\beta \Theta$ (20)

solids pressure and bulk viscosity:
 $p_s^{\text{kc}} = \alpha_s \rho_s \left(\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\alpha'}} + 4\eta_s \alpha_s g_0 \right) \Theta$, $\lambda_s^{\text{kc}} = \frac{8}{3} \eta_s \alpha_s^2 \rho_s d_s g_0 \sqrt{\frac{\Theta}{\pi}}$ (21)

Boundary conditions for solid phase:
 $\tau_s^{\text{kc}} = -\eta_w \mu_w \alpha_s \rho_s g_0 \Theta \text{erf}(\bar{u}_s) \frac{\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}}{\|\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}\|}$, $\mu_0 = \frac{7}{2} \frac{1+e_{p-w}}{1+\beta_0} \mu_w$, $\eta_w = \frac{1}{2} (1 + e_{p-w})$, $\bar{u}_s = \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}\|}{\sqrt{2}\mu_0}$, (22)

$\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q} = \tau_s^{\text{kc}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}} - \frac{2\mu_w g_0 \eta_w \sqrt{\Theta}}{\sqrt{2} \mu_0^2 \sqrt{\pi}} \exp(-\bar{u}_s^2) \left\{ \mu_w \left[2\mu_w \|\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}\|^2 (2\eta_w - \mu_0) + \Theta (14\mu_w \eta_w - 4\mu_0 (1 + \mu_w) - 6\mu_w \mu_0^2 \eta_w) \right] \right.$
 $\left. + \mu_0^2 \sqrt{\Theta} \exp(\bar{u}_s^2) \left[\sqrt{\Theta} (4(\eta_w - 1) + 6\mu_w^2 \eta_w) - \sqrt{2\pi} \mu_w \|\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}\| \text{erf}(\bar{u}_s) \right] \right\}$. (23)

force, the virtual mass force, as well as the Saffman and Magnus lift forces are neglected in this study. As studied by Goniva et al. (Goniva et al., 2012), rolling friction which accounts for the small-scale non-sphericity of particles, influences the solids velocities in the single-spout fluidized bed, thus, particle-particle and particle-wall torques, \mathbf{T}_i , are supplemented by a constant directional torque (Ai et al., 2011),

$$\mathbf{T}_i = \sum_{i \neq j} R_i \mathbf{n}_{ij} \times \mathbf{F}^{(t)} + \sum_{i \neq j} \mathbf{T}_{ij}^{(\text{roll,fric.})} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_{ij}^{(\text{roll,fric.})} = -\mu_r R^* \mathbf{F}^{(n)} \frac{\omega_r}{|\omega_r|} \quad (9)$$

where μ_r rolling friction coefficient and ω_r is relative angular velocity (Zhou et al., 1999).

2.2. TFM

2.2.1. Governing equations

The averaged mass and momentum equations for fluid and solid phases are written as (Agrawal et al., 2001; Ishii, 1975)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_q \rho_q) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{u}_q) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \alpha_f \boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \beta_{TFM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s) + \alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{g} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s \mathbf{u}_s) = -\alpha_s \nabla p - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{S}_s^{\text{kc}} + \mathbf{S}_s^{\text{fr}}) + \beta_{TFM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s) + \alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{g} \quad (12)$$

where in Eq. (10), \mathbf{u}_q , α_q and ρ_q are the velocity, volume fraction and density of phase q where q represents either the solid phase or fluid phase, $q = s, f$. Also, β_{TFM} is the interphase drag force coefficient in the TFM approach. Following Section 2.1.1, a Newtonian deviatoric stress is considered for gas stress–strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$.

2.2.2. Kinetic–collisional stresses

For solids volume fraction up to 40%, it has been accepted that solids stresses are arising from translational movement of particles (kinetic contribution) and particle–particle collisions (collisional contribution) and in case of high number of particles involved, the kinetic theory of granular flows is applied to close the kinetic–collisional solids stress tensor, \mathbf{S}_s^{kc} (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012; Van Wachem et al., 2001). Due to the dependency of the kinetic–collisional solids stresses on the particle velocity fluctuations, there is a need to supplement mass and momentum equations with a balance of pseudo-thermal energy (PTE), as shown in Eq. (13), where granular temperature is defined as $\Theta = 2/3E_{PT}$. Eq. (14) represents kinetic–collisional solids stress tensor with considering expansion and compression of the granular solids where p_s^{kc} and λ_s^{kc} are solids pressure and bulk viscosity as denoted in Eq. (21). In Eq. (13), the first term at the RHS ($-\mathbf{S}_s^{\text{kc}} : \nabla \mathbf{u}_s$) denotes production of PTE due to kinetic–collisional solids shear, due to the assumption that work done by \mathbf{S}_s^{fr} is totally converted into thermal internal energy, \mathbf{S}_s^{fr} does not contribute to the PTE balance (Srivastava and Sundaresan, 2003). The second term ($-\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}$) represents diffusion of the PTE. The third, Γ_s , and forth, J_v , terms are depicting transition of kinetic energy of particle velocity fluctuations to fluid phase. The fifth term, γ_Θ , is rate of dissipation of PTE due to inelastic particle collisions. Following (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012; Agrawal et al., 2001) solids viscosity, μ_s^{kc} , and the PTE flux vector, \mathbf{q} , are including the effect of interstitial fluid by μ^* and κ^* , respectively. Moreover, Hrenya and Sinclair (Hrenya and Sinclair, 1997) and Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) considered the effect of bounding walls in μ_s^{kc} , \mathbf{q} and p_s^{kc} terms by limiting the mean free path of particle, l_s , using $1/(1 + l_s/\mathbb{L})$ where \mathbb{L} is characteristic length scale of the bed. Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) developed improved boundary conditions for solids stresses and outward flux of fluctuation energy which integrates the particle–wall sliding and non-sliding collisions. Eqs. (22) and (23) represent wall shear stresses arising from kinetic–collisional stresses of the solid phase, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{kc}}$, and normal flux of fluctuation energy, $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q}$, respectively. The first term at RHS of Eq. (23) is generation of the PTE and the second term denotes dissipation. In addition, e_{p-w} and β_0 are normal and tangential restitution coefficients at walls, respectively. μ_w is the wall friction coefficient. These boundary conditions have shown good results when applied to the spout fluidized bed simulations (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012; Schneiderbauer et al., 2012).

2.2.3. Frictional stresses

At high solids volume fractions ($\alpha_s \gtrsim 0.4$, (Forterre and Pouliquen, 2008)), inter-particle collisions are not binary anymore and particles experience long-lasting sliding contacts, therefore solids stress closures based on the KTGF are not valid anymore. This in turn, implies that other closures are needed for solids stresses at frictional regimes. Therefore, the total solids stress tensor can be expressed as (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012)

$$\mathbf{S}_s = \mathbf{S}_s^{\text{kc}} + \mathbf{S}_s^{\text{fr}} \quad (24)$$

where frictional solids stresses can be written as rigid-plastic rheological model (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012)

$$\mathbf{S}_s^{\text{fr}} = p_s^{\text{fr}} \mathbf{I} - 2\mu_s^{\text{fr}}(I_s, p_s^{\text{fr}}, \text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s) \text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s \quad (25)$$

with

$$\mu_s^{\text{fr}}(I_s, p_s^{\text{fr}}, \text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s) = \frac{\mu_i(I_s)p_s^{\text{fr}}}{2\|\text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s\|} \quad (26)$$

where inertial number, I_s , is

$$I_s = \frac{2\|\text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s\|d_s}{\sqrt{p_s^{\text{fr}}/\rho_s}} \quad (27)$$

Chialvo et al. (Chialvo et al., 2012) proposed a model of normal frictional stresses for different ranges of solids volume fraction in the frictional regime that incorporates the various regimes' contributions and can be expressed as

$$p_s^{\text{fr}} = \begin{cases} p_s^{\text{QS}} + p_s^{\text{int}} & \text{for } \alpha_s \geq \alpha_s^{\text{max}} \\ \left((p_s^{\text{inert}})^{-1} + (p_s^{\text{int}})^{-1} \right)^{-1} & \text{for } \alpha_s < \alpha_s^{\text{max}} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where p_s^{QS} , p_s^{int} and p_s^{inert} denote quasi-static, intermediate and inertial regimes contributions and take the form (Chialvo et al., 2012)

$$\frac{p_s^{\text{QS}}d_s}{k} = \alpha_{\text{QS}}\|\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{\text{max}}\|^{2/3} \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{p_s^{\text{int}}d_s}{k} = \alpha_{\text{int}}\hat{\gamma}_s^{1/2} \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{p_s^{\text{inert}}d_s}{k} = \frac{\alpha_{\text{inert}}\hat{\gamma}_s^2}{\|\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{\text{max}}\|^2} \quad (31)$$

where the scaled shear rate is defined as

$$\hat{\gamma}_s = \frac{2\|\text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s\|d_s}{\sqrt{k/(\rho_s d_s)}}, \quad (32)$$

and d_s , k and α_s^{max} are the particle diameter, the particle stiffness and the maximum packing. Furthermore, α_{QS} , α_{int} and α_{inert} denote the model parameters and can be found in Table 5. As mentioned by Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2015), substituting Eq. (32) into p_s^{inert} reveals that p_s^{inert} is not dependent on the particle stiffness which reads

$$p_s^{\text{inert}} = 4\rho_s\alpha_{\text{inert}}\left(\frac{\|\text{dev}\mathbf{D}_s\|d_s}{\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{\text{max}}}\right)^2 \quad (33)$$

It has to be noted that in Eq. (17), radial distribution function, g_0 , has been truncated using the value of α_s^{min} for the solids volume fractions larger than α_s^{min} , therefore the kinetic pressure contribution of solids pressure comes from Eq. (33) instead of Eq. (21). Chialvo et al. (Chialvo et al., 2012) also suggested a $\mu(I)$ -rheology to close the frictional shear stresses, $\mu_i(I_s)p_s^{\text{fr}}$, and can be written as

$$\mu_i(I_s) = \mu_i^{\text{st}} + \frac{\alpha_1}{(I_0/I_s)^{\beta_1} + 1} \quad (34)$$

where μ_i^{st} , α_1 , I_0 and β_1 are the model parameters and presented at Table 5. Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) suggested a normal frictional stress closure with inertial number dependent frictional viscosity. This model takes form of

$$p_s^{\text{fr}} = \begin{cases} p_s^{\text{QS}} & \text{for } \alpha_s \geq \alpha_s^{\text{max}} \\ p_s^{\text{inert}} & \text{for } \alpha_s < \alpha_s^{\text{max}} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

where p_s^{QS} and p_s^{inert} were defined in Eq. (29) and Eq. (33), respectively. Also, their model uses the same rheological form of $\mu_i(I_s)$ as Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) with a difference in parameter β_1 which is 1.0 in Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012). Furthermore, it can be deduced that Chialvo (Chialvo et al., 2012) and Schneiderbauer (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) frictional stress closures do not

depend on the empirical parameter of minimum solids volume fraction, α_s^{\min} . A closer look on the expression of Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012), reveals that the calculated normal frictional stress for $\alpha_s < \alpha_s^{\max}$ will be less than the individual contribution from any of the intermediate and inertial regimes frictional stress. This implies that the frictional solids stresses obtained from this closure at the same conditions will be lower than Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) prediction. Fig. 1 which compares predicted values of the normal frictional stresses from both closures in the packed state ($\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{\max} = 0.01$) justifies this fact. Finally, it should be noted that p_s^{QS} in Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and $p_s^{\text{QS}} + p_s^{\text{int}}$ expression in Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) were added for $\alpha_s \geq \alpha_s^{\max}$, because of the numerical reasons to ensure that the solids volume fraction will not exceed the maximum packing limit. Similar to the kinetic–collisional stresses, considering the frictional solids stresses contribution in wall shear stresses is essential in TFM simulations (Nigmatova et al., 2022) and one should distinguish between sliding and non-sliding collisions. Therefore as developed by Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012), the contribution of frictional solids stresses in case of non-sliding collision can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr,ns}} = \left\| \mathbf{S}_s^{\text{fr}} \cdot \mathbf{n} - (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{S}_s^{\text{fr}} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \cdot \mathbf{n} \right\| \quad (36)$$

and in case of sliding collisions we have

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr,sl}} = \mu_w \left\| \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{S}_s^{\text{fr}} \cdot \mathbf{n} \right\| \quad (37)$$

Hence, the frictional wall shear stresses can be expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr}} = -\frac{\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}}{\|\mathbf{u}_s^{\text{sl}}\|} \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr,ns}} & \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr,ns}} < \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr,sl}} \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr,sl}} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

Then the total wall shear stresses are the sum of the frictional and kinetic–collisional solids stresses,

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_s = \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{fr}} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^{\text{kc}} \quad (39)$$

Fig. 1. Comparison of the normal frictional stresses from Schneiderbauer (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and Chialvo (Chialvo et al., 2012) frictional stress closures at $\alpha_s < \alpha_s^{\max}$ using $\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{\max} = 0.01, k = 10^4$ N/m (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) and the model parameters for $\mu_r = 0.0$ in Table 5.

2.2.4. Rolling friction effect in TFM

As discussed by Schneiderbauer et al. (2015), impact of the rolling friction on the frictional stresses is not negligible. Therefore Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2015) proposed to add the rolling friction coefficient linearly to the inter-particle friction coefficient by assuming one-dimensional frictional shear flow. However, when we applied this modification to our TFM simulations, we found that the time-averaged downward solids velocity profiles near the side walls show higher values with adding the rolling friction while the opposite observed from our CFD-DEM simulations (results not shown here) and CFD-DEM simulations of Hu et al. (Hu et al., 2019). In order to consider the influence of rolling friction in TFM simulations, we suggest a new ad hoc modification to include the effect of the rolling friction in the $\mu(I)$ -rheology through angle of repose (AOR) measurements. Thus, we performed DEM simulations of the formation of a pile using the material properties and simulation parameters reported in Table 8 and measured the AOR (not shown here). The values of measured AOR are presented in Table 4. The value of the AOR with $\mu_r = 0.0$ is close to the value of 20.2° reported in the literature (Frankowski and Morgeneyer, 2013) for glass bead particles with the diameter of 3 mm.

Based on the values of $\mu_i^{\text{st}} = \sin(\text{AOR})$, we obtained μ_p and α_{QS} from the data of Chialvo et al. (Chialvo et al., 2012) (see Table 2 in (Chialvo et al., 2012)) by interpolation. Furthermore, as shown by Singh et al. (Singh et al., 2020), the maximum solids volume fraction of dense granular suspensions decreases with increasing the rolling friction. This, in turn, implies that is of vital importance to additionally adjust the value of α_s^{\max} based on the modified μ_p , which accounts for the rolling friction (see Table 1 in (Chialvo et al., 2012)). Table 5 lists the frictional stress closures constants with respect to the rolling friction coefficients used in this study.

2.3. Interphase drag force in TFM and CFD-DEM

Interphase drag force is the important source of momentum exchange between fluid and solids. Table 6 summarizes the four different interphase drag coefficients studied in this paper. The interphase drag coefficient correlations are either obtained through measurements of pressure drop and terminal velocity of sedimenting particles or via accurate direct numerical simulations (DNS). However, it should be noted that parameters in empirically obtained correlations are exclusively for experimental conditions which particles are not ideally monodisperse and also those correlations do not account for all range of possible situations occurring in gas–solid systems. The model of Wen and Yu (Wen, 1966) is one of the empirically obtained interphase drag models which is widely used in simulations of fluid–solid systems. The other three drag correlations (Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007), Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011) and Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015)) in the Table 6 were obtained from DNS. The DNS interphase drag models cover a broad range of Re numbers and α_s as presented in Table 6. It is clear that all interphase drag models are functions of Re number and α_s and the models of the Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) and Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007) are valid for a wider range of Re numbers and α_s than the model of Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011). Nonetheless, as discussed by Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011) and Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015), the drag model of Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007) shows discrep-

Table 4
AOR values measured from DEM simulations.

μ_r	0.0	0.06	0.125
AOR	20°	22°	23°

Table 5
Parameters of frictional stresses closures.

μ_r -Dependent parameters						
μ_r	0.0	0.06	0.125			
μ_i^{st}	0.34	0.38	0.39			
α_{QS}	0.10	0.20	0.21			
α_s^{max}	0.60	0.587	0.585			
μ_r -Independent parameters						
α_{inert}	α_{int}	I_0	α_1	β_1 (Chialvo closure)	β_1 (Sch. closure)	
0.021	0.099	0.32	0.37	1.5	1.0	

Table 6
Interphase drag coefficient correlations.

Correlation	Interphase drag coefficient	Re	α_s
Wen and Yu (Wen, 1966)	$\beta = \frac{3}{4} C_D \frac{\rho_f z_f \alpha_s \mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s }{d_p} \alpha_f^{-2.65}$ <p>with $C_D = \begin{cases} 24/Re (1 + 0.15Re^{0.687}) & Re < 1000 \\ 0.44 & Re \geq 1000 \end{cases}$</p> $Re = \frac{\alpha_s \rho_f d_p \mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s }{\mu_f}$		
Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007)	$\beta = 180 \frac{\mu_f z_f^2}{d_p^2 z_f} + 18 \frac{\mu_f z_f^2 \alpha_s (1 + 1.5\sqrt{\alpha_s})}{d_p^2}$ $+ 0.31 \frac{\mu_f z_f Re}{d_p^2 z_f} \left[\frac{\alpha_f^{-1} + 3z_f \alpha_s + 8.4Re^{-0.343}}{1 + 10^{3z_f} Re^{-0.5 - 2z_f}} \right]$	$20 < Re < 1000$	up to 0.6
Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011)	$\beta = 18 \frac{\mu_f z_f (1 + 0.15Re^{0.687})}{d_p^2 z_f} + 104.58 \frac{\mu_f z_f^2}{d_p^2 z_f}$ $+ 8.64 \frac{\mu_f z_f^4}{d_p^2 z_f^2} + \frac{18 \mu_f z_f^2 \alpha_s^4 Re}{d_p^2} \left[0.95 + \frac{0.61 z_f^2}{z_f} \right]$	$Re \leq 300$	up to 0.5
Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015)	$\beta = 180 \frac{\mu_f z_f^2}{d_p^2 z_f} + 18 \frac{\mu_f z_f^2 \alpha_s (1 + 1.5\sqrt{\alpha_s})}{d_p^2} + \frac{18 \mu_f z_f \alpha_s Re}{d_p^2}$ $\left[0.11 \alpha_s (1 + \alpha_s) - \frac{0.00456}{z_f} + \left(0.169 \alpha_f + \frac{0.0644}{z_f} \right) Re^{-0.343} \right]$	$Re \leq 1000$	up to 0.6

ancies with their data at high Re numbers and α_s values. These deviations originate mainly from the large grid size in the DNS simulations employed by Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007) for $0.2 \leq \alpha_s \leq 0.6$ (Tang et al., 2015). Furthermore, it should be mentioned that none of the interphase drag correlations listed in Table 6 includes the pressure gradient force effect. Lastly, the interphase drag coefficient of a particle in CFD-DEM simulations can be obtained by $\beta_{DEM} = \beta_{TFM} \frac{\pi d_p^3}{6 \alpha_s}$.

3. Simulations

In CFD-DEM simulations, we coupled LIGGGHTS for DEM and OpenFOAM for CFD through CFDEMcoupling framework (Goniva et al., 2012). Also, we performed TFM simulations in OpenFOAM using a modified version of *twoPhaseEulerFoam* named *twoPhaseEulerTurbFoam* (<https://github.com/ParticulateFlow/pfmFOAM-public>) to account for the Eqs. (10)–(12), (24)–(35). The experimental data of the multiple-spout fluidized bed with Geldart D particles by van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) was used to validate CFD-DEM and TFM simulations. They employed Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) and Positron Emission Particle Tracking (PEPT) methods to measure time averaged solids velocities at three different heights in the single- and multiple-spout fluidized beds. The geometry of the multiple-spout fluidized bed is presented in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the geometry of the bed is pseudo-2D and the effect of front and back walls are considerable in the simulations. To be consistent with the experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) a windbox was considered in the bottom of the bed in order to link the pressure drop of the spouts in the multiple-spout fluidized bed. As explained by van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) spouting gas flow in the multiple-spout fluidized beds was fed from the windbox, thus

based on the velocity of the spouting gas flow \mathbf{u}_g^{sp} , gas flow velocity in the windbox inlet, \mathbf{u}_g^{wb} , was obtained using Eq. (40) and used as the boundary value in the simulations. The gas flow velocities are listed in Table 7.

$$\mathbf{u}_g^{wb} = \frac{n^{sp} A^{sp}}{A^{wb}} \mathbf{u}_g^{sp} \quad (40)$$

where n^{sp} , A^{sp} and A^{wb} are number of spouts, cross section area of single spout and cross section area of windbox, respectively. Initial bed volume fraction of $\alpha_s = 0.58$ was chosen for all TFM simulations.

In both CFD-DEM and TFM simulations, no-slip boundary condition was applied to the gas phase velocity at the walls. It should be mentioned that due to having large particles compared to grid size, applying no-slip BC for gas phase at the wall will not lead to unrealistic results for the fluid velocity seen by particles in our CFD-DEM simulations. Moreover, Eqs. (22)–(23) and Eqs. (36)–(39) were employed as the solid phase boundary condition at the walls in TFM simulations. At the inlet of the windbox, uniform gas velocity was specified and atmospheric pressure was used at the top of outlet. Time discretization was achieved by first-order implicit Euler method in both of CFD-DEM and TFM simulations where constant and adjustable time step settings were used in CFD-DEM and TFM simulations while the time step was limiting by the maximum Courant number (CFL) of 1.0. The spatial discretization of convective and diffusion terms were attained by Gauss linear method in both approaches. The PIMPLE algorithm which is the combination of Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations (SIMPLE) method and Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operators (PISO) method was utilized for the pressure-velocity coupling of the Navier–Stokes equations. For all TFM and CFD-DEM simulations a grid spacing of 5 mm was used. This grid spacing size was chosen

Fig. 2. The sketch of the multiple-spout fluidized bed of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). The dashed lines are the borders of the cells of which double- and triple-spout fluidized bed are comprised. The gray area represents the windbox, u_g^{bg} is background gas velocity and u_g^{sp} is spouting gas flow velocity. The units are in mm.

Table 7

Gas flow velocities u_g^{bg} , u_g^{sp} and u_g^{wb} as well as number of particles N_p used in the simulations.

Property	Single-spout	Double-spout	Triple-spout	Unit
u_g^{bg}	2.4	2.4	2.3	m.s ⁻¹
u_g^{sp}	43.5	40.5	43.8	m.s ⁻¹
u_g^{wb}		1.4	1.5	m.s ⁻¹
N_p	12000	48000	107000	-

Table 8

Material properties and CFD-DEM and TFM simulations parameters extracted from Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and Goniva et al. (Goniva et al., 2012).

Property	value	Unit
d_s	3	mm
μ_f	1.78×10^{-5}	kg.m ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹
ρ_f	1.1	kg.m ⁻³
ρ_s	2505	kg.m ⁻³
e_{p-p}	0.9	-
e_{p-w}	0.9	-
β_0 (TFM)	0.4	-
μ_w (TFM)	0.34, 0.38, 0.39	-
μ_{p-p} (CFD-DEM)	0.2	-
μ_{p-w}	0.2	-
$\mu_{r,p-p}$	0.0, 0.06, 0.125	-
$\mu_{r,p-w}$	0.0, 0.06, 0.125	-
ν (CFD-DEM)	0.45	-
E (CFD-DEM)	1.0×10^7	kg.m ⁻¹ .s ⁻²
CFD time step (CFD-DEM)	1.0×10^{-4}	s
DEM time step (CFD-DEM)	5×10^{-6}	s
TFM time step	adjustable time step, CFL < 1.0	s
Simulation time	40	s

based on the grid size sensitivity studies of Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and Yang et al. (Yang et al., 2016) on the same experimental case (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) that was also used in this study for validations. Eventually, the simulation parameters and material properties are listed in Table 8. Note

that three different values of μ_r were used where the maximum value was reported in Goniva et al. (Goniva et al., 2012) for the single-spout fluidized bed simulations. Also, the values of particle-wall friction coefficient, μ_w , in TFM simulations are based on the rolling friction coefficient values.

4. Results

For brevity, in this section, we will abbreviate TFM simulations with Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) with just "TFM" and TFM simulations with Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) with "TFM (Schneiderbauer)". We used a workstation with an 8-core CPU of 2.93 GHz frequency and 48 GB RAM for all the simulations. The required computational time for 1 s of TFM and CFD-DEM simulations in the single-spout fluidized bed was about 799 s and 1205 s, respectively. Also, it took 2475 s for 1 s of TFM simulations in the double-spout fluidized bed while it was 4628 s for 1 s of CFD-DEM simulations. In addition, for 1 s of TFM and CFD-DEM simulations in the triple-spout fluidized bed, the computational time was 9685 s and 14731 s, respectively.

4.1. Single-spout fluidized bed

In order to examine the effect of interphase drag models on hydrodynamics of single-spout fluidized bed, TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with the interphase drag correlations of Table 6 are performed. Due to the fact that Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) is more sophisticated than Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012), Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) is adopted to validate the TFM results with experiments. Figs. 3 and 4 compares the time averaged vertical solids velocities extracted from TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with PIV and PEPT measurements and CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). Qualitatively, all the interphase drag models used in both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches are correctly predicting the spouting flow regime where the solid phase is carried upward by the spouting gas flow in the spout region and then falls down on the bed surface due to the gravity in the fountain region, then the solids move downward in the annulus region to enter the spout from regions close to the spouting gas inlet. At $z = 50$ mm, in both TFM and CFD-DEM simulations, all the interphase

Fig. 3. Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from TFM with the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the single-spout fluidized bed. The solid blue line indicates the CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). (a, b) $z = 50$ mm and (c, d) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width.

drag models show only slight discrepancies with the experimental measurements in terms of the solids velocities in the spout region and near the side walls in the annulus region. Especially models of the Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) and Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011), indicate great agreement with the experimental data of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). Similarly, at $z = 100$ mm, all drag models display fair accordance with the experimental data of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in terms of the solids velocities in the spout region. However near the side walls models of the Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) and Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011) predict more accurate profiles. The overestimation of the downward solids velocities at $z = 100$ mm, which is located near to the bed surface in the experiments, from the drag models of Beetstra et al. (Beetstra et al., 2007) and Wen and Yu (Wen, 1966) is because of the lower bed surface expansion that leads

to the placement of $z = 100$ mm in the fountain region where the downward solids velocities are higher. A comparison in terms of the rolling friction coefficient values of 0.06 and 0.125 shows that its effect has been captured in TFM simulations same as CFD-DEM simulations near the side walls in a way that increasing the rolling friction leads to lower downward solids velocities because of increasing particle-wall friction. Although the effect is not pronounced in TFM simulations which originates from the fact that increasing μ_r from 0.06 to 0.125 does not change the rheological parameters considerably (Table 5). Also, it can be seen that with increasing the rolling friction peak velocity decreases slightly. Furthermore, at $z = 100$ mm, the solids velocities profile from CFD-DEM simulation of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) overpredicts the downward solids velocities. The authors attributed the overestimation to the inappropriate particle-wall interactions

Fig. 4. Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from CFD-DEM with the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the single-spout fluidized bed. The solid blue line indicates the CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). (a, b) $z = 50$ mm and (c, d) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The "DEM" notation in the figure legend corresponds to CFD-DEM simulations.

of their CFD-DEM model. Therefore, as shown by Goniva et al. (Goniva et al., 2012) and here, incorporating the particle-wall rolling friction improves the solids velocities profiles to an acceptable level. A closer look at the Figs. 3 and 4 reveals that the single-spout fluidized bed with $\mu_r = 0.06$ shows better results near the side walls, therefore $\mu_r = 0.06$ will be used in the simulations of the single-spout fluidized bed. For further comparison of the hydrodynamics of the single- and multiple-spout fluidized beds with TFM and CFD-DEM approaches, one has to be consistent in using the interphase drag force in both approaches. Based on the presented results, interphase drag model of Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) matches experimental results quite well in both approaches and it also covers wider ranges of Re numbers and α_s than drag model of Tenneti et al. (Tenneti et al., 2011), hence the single- and multiple-spout fluidized bed simulations will be performed with the interphase drag model

of Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015). Finally, we calculated the root mean square error (RMSE) between simulation results using $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the interphase drag model of Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) with the experiments. It was found that at $z = 50$ mm, CFD-DEM and TFM predictions have RMSE of 0.039 and 0.043 against the PIV measurements and RMSE of 0.039 and 0.041 compared to the PEPT measurements. Furthermore, at $z = 100$ mm, CFD-DEM and TFM results show RMSE of 0.11 and 0.15 in comparison with the PIV data and RMSE of 0.028 and 0.063 against the PEPT measurements. Therefore, it can be concluded that CFD-DEM results using $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the interphase drag model of Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) match the experiments better than TFM simulations.

Fig. 5 represents the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM at three different heights and experimental data of van Buijtenen et al.

Fig. 5. A Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.06 in the single-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 50$ mm, (b) $z = 75$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. It should be noted that the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) were available only at $z = 50$ and 100 mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

Fig. 6. Variation of the laterally and time averaged solids volume fraction along height from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.06 in the single-spout fluidized bed. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

(van Buijtenen et al., 2011) are provided at $z = 50$ and 100 mm. It should be mentioned that TFM (Schneiderbauer) simulations are presented just at $\mu_r = 0.06$. It can be seen that with neglecting the rolling friction, the solids velocities increase near the the side walls due to decreasing of the particle-wall friction and the simulation results deviate to a larger extent from the experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). Furthermore, this supports that the present ad hoc modification for including the rolling friction in TFM (Section 2.2.4) is successfully mimicking the effect of the rolling friction in the same manner as CFD-DEM. There are small discrepancies in the maximum solids velocities values between TFM and CFD-DEM at $z = 50$ and 75 mm, however, the difference gets larger between TFM and CFD-DEM with $\mu_r = 0.06$ at $z = 100$ mm. In addition, the maximum solids velocities in the spout increases with neglecting rolling friction leading to a lower deviation between the simulations and the experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). A similar finding has also been reported by Hu et al. (Hu et al., 2019). Neglecting the rolling friction yields lower heights, resulting to higher downward particle velocities at $z = 100$ mm. In particular, $z = 100$ mm is consequently located in the fountain region and not within the bed. Finally, a comparison between TFM and TFM (Schneiderbauer) unveils that at $z = 50$ mm both frictional closures predict quite same profiles, but with moving along the bed height, TFM (Schneiderbauer) yields to lower solids velocities in the spout. In addition, at $z = 100$ mm, it can be seen that the solids velocities of TFM (Schneiderbauer) in the annulus

Fig. 7. Time averaged solids volume fraction profiles obtained from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM in the single-spout fluidized bed.

Fig. 8. A Comparison of the time averaged solids volume fraction from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.06 in the single-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 50$ mm, (b) $z = 75$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

region is lower than TFM, indicating that the bed surface height is higher with TFM (Schneiderbauer). It can be further seen that at the all heights, the downward solids velocities are lower in TFM (Schneiderbauer), which is due to higher wall shear stresses as the frictional solids stresses are higher in Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012). Therefore, it can be concluded that the frictional stresses have significant influence on the results.

To justify the fact that neglecting the rolling friction leads to the variation of the bed surface, the laterally and time averaged solids volume fraction profiles with the bed height are presented in Fig. 6. It should be mentioned that lateral averaging is done by averaging over all cells in the bed cross section at every height and we use $\langle \rangle_l$ operator to denote lateral and temporal averaging. From this figure, it can be interpreted that in general, the solids volume fraction is higher in the annulus region and gradually decreases along the bed height till the bed surface height then it decreases with a steep slope with some fluctuations in the solids volume fraction in the fountain region. Also, the small increase in the solids volume fraction of CFD-DEM in the area close to the spouting gas inlet, is due to the fact that particles mostly are entering the spout from this area ($z=[0-10]$ mm). It can be found that the bed surface height of TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ is lower than the others which results in higher downward solids velocities near the side walls as shown in Fig. 5. On the other hand, it can be seen that expansion of TFM (Schneiderbauer) is higher due to higher wall shear stresses. Moreover, Fig. 6 reveals that the fountain height is approximately 10 mm higher in CFD-DEM.

The time averaged solids volume fraction profiles extracted from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM are presented in Fig. 7. Three distinct regions including the annulus region with higher solids volume fraction located along the walls, the spout region in the center and the umbrella-shaped fountain region on top of the bed surface can be distinguished in Fig. 7. Further, neglecting the rolling friction results in higher solids volume fraction at the top of the fountain region, which is due to lower particle-particle and particle-wall frictions that facilitates particle's movement into the spout from the annulus and TFM predicts this behavior as CFD-DEM. A comparison between the solids volume fraction profiles of TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM reveals that both closures predict quite similar profiles, however a quantitative comparison can unveil the possible differences. To gain quantitative comparison, the time averaged profiles of solids volume fraction at three heights are plotted in Fig. 8. As can be inferred from Figs. 8a and 8b, including the rolling friction decreases the solids volume fraction in the spout and annulus regions in both TFM and CFD-DEM, also TFM predicts slightly higher solids volume frac-

tions in annulus region than CFD-DEM. The TFM (Schneiderbauer) shows lower solids volume fractions in the annulus region than TFM which can be attributed to the larger predicted frictional solids stresses from Schneiderbauer closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) in dense regions as shown in Fig. 1. This observation is inline with van Wachem et al. (Van Wachem et al., 2001), which showed that with increasing the solids stresses, solids volume fraction decreases. Also, TFM (Schneiderbauer) has lower solids volume fractions in the spout region. As discussed before in Fig. 6, at $z = 100$ mm due to the variation of the bed surface height, TFM and CFD-DEM with $\mu_r = 0.06$ show higher solids volume fractions than simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$, revealing $z = 100$ mm places on the bed surface height.

Fig. 9 presents the time averaged solids axial flux profiles as a representation to the solids circulation rate in the bed, which is calculated with

$$\langle \phi_z \rangle = \langle \rho_s \alpha_s V_z \rangle \quad (41)$$

where ϕ_z are the time averaging operator and the solids axial flux. In both TFM and CFD-DEM, the solids are entrained upward in the spout region and flow downward in the annulus region. Also, as moving along the bed height, the downward solids flux grows notably larger in the annulus, And the upward solids axial flux decreases at $z = 100$ mm where the solids momentum is dissipated by gravitational force in the spout. As explained in the Fig. 5 about the effect of excluding the rolling friction near the side walls, this effect also is obvious here in both TFM and CFD-DEM as the downward flux of solids increases near the side walls by neglecting the rolling friction. It is interesting to note that while TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM show matching profiles in Fig. 5 at $z = 50$ mm, the solids axial flux profiles show discrepancies and TFM (Schneiderbauer) predicts lower axial fluxes.

In order to further investigate the capabilities of TFM approach in comparison with CFD-DEM approach, it is essential to study the predicted values of granular temperature that account for particle-particle collisions in TFM simulations (Fox, 2014) with CFD-DEM simulations. CFD-DEM approach explicitly solves the equations presented in Table 2 to calculate the particle-particle collision. The granular temperature is a measure of random motion of particles in a certain small spatial scale. In the sense of thermodynamics, temperature of a gas is an indicator of the kinetic energy of gas molecules, and in the same manner based on the KTGF the granular temperature is a representation of the pseudo-thermal energy of the solid particles. Capecelatro et al. (Capecelatro et al., 2015) revealed that as long as the number of particles inside a cell is greater than 10, particle fluctuating energy is independent of number of particles inside the cell. In the case of the grid resolution

Fig. 9. The time averaged solids axial flux from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.06 in the single-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 50$ mm, (b) $z = 75$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

employed for CFD-DEM in this study, the number of particles is less than 10 within the spout region. Therefore, we computed the granular temperature from the CFD-DEM simulations in a post-processing step using a grid size of (10 mm \times 10 mm \times 5 mm). This grid size ensures that the number of particles inside the cells is greater than 10. Also, it should be mentioned that due to the small thickness of the bed, we ignored the particle velocity fluctuations in the bed thickness (y -direction). For the TFM simulations, the granular temperature can be calculated by solving the Eq. (13). To be consistent in calculating the granular temperature between both approaches, again, in a post-processing step, we applied a box filter of the same size as the CFD-DEM post-processing grid to the TFM results. In CFD-DEM approach, the normal components of the particle velocity fluctuation tensor, Θ_k , should be evaluated as

$$\Theta_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\mathbf{u}_{i,k}(t) - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k@i}(t) \right]^2, k = x, z \quad (42)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{u}_{i,k}(t) \quad (43)$$

where n depicts the number of particles in the cell, $\mathbf{u}_{i,k}(t)$ is the instantaneous velocity of the particle i inside the grid cell. Also, \sim is the local averaging operator and $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k(t)$ is the instantaneous locally

averaged particle velocity inside the cell. In Eq. (42), $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k@i}(t)$ is the instantaneous locally averaged particle velocity linearly interpolated to the particle position. The same procedure has been applied by Gu et al. (Gu et al., 2019) to calculate granular temperature. After evaluating the normal components of the particle velocity fluctuation tensor, the granular temperature in cells, Θ , can be obtained with

$$\Theta = \frac{1}{2} (\Theta_x + \Theta_z) \quad (44)$$

Fig. 10 shows the time averaged granular temperature from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations at different heights. It can be seen that in both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches, the granular temperature in the spout decreases with height, similar finding has reported by Deb and Tafti (Deb and Tafti, 2014), and at $z = 50$ and 75 mm in the annulus region, the granular temperature is almost zero, indicating that randomness of the particles is very low. A comparison between CFD-DEM and TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ depicts that at $z = 50$ and 75 mm, TFM shows higher granular temperature in the spout than CFD-DEM. Also, it can be seen that at all heights, including the rolling friction does not influence the results in CFD-DEM simulations significantly in the spout region. However including the rolling friction in TFM changes the granular temperature remarkably in the spout region. A possible explanation for the significant inconsistency between the predicted values of the granular temperature from TFM and CFD-DEM with $\mu_r = 0.06$ in the spout region can be related to the incor-

Fig. 10. A Comparison of the time averaged granular temperature from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.06 in the single-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 50$ mm, (b) $z = 75$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

Fig. 11. Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from TFM and CFD-DEM with the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the double-spout fluidized bed with $\mu_r = 0.06$ and 0.125 . The solid blue line indicates the CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). (a, b) $z = 20$ mm, (c, d) $z = 50$ mm and (e, f) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width.

rect predictions of the boundary condition of the pseudo-thermal energy flux (Eq. (23)), at the front and back walls of the pseudo-2D bed. As shown by Schneiderbauer et al. (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) the pseudo-thermal energy flux increases with increasing the coefficient of wall friction. Therefore, as listed in Table 8, increasing the rolling friction leads to higher values of wall friction coefficient in TFM simulations that result in higher flux of pseudo-thermal energy at the front and back walls. Thus, higher values of the granular temperature is obtained in the spout region. Neglecting the rolling friction leads to a lower bed surface height, thus at $z = 100$ mm, higher values of the granular temperature are obtained near the side walls in comparison with these simulations with the rolling friction. This originates from the higher randomness of the particles motion in the fountain region. The comparison between TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM simulations shows that granular temperature is higher in the spout for TFM (Schneiderbauer), arising from the lower solid volume fractions in the spout for Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) as illustrated in Fig. 7, which leads to less particle–particle collisions and, as a result, less damping of the PTE. Finally, it can be concluded, that TFM results can qualitatively predict the variations of the granular temperature in the bed similar to CFD-DEM. However, in a quantitative comparison sense, TFM yields higher granular temperature values than CFD-DEM, which grow with including the rolling friction.

4.2. Double-spout fluidized bed

As mentioned in Section 4.1, the drag model of Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) is applied for the multiple-spout bed simulations. In the double-spout fluidized bed, the corresponding spouting gas and background velocities in Table 7 lead to multiple-interacting-spouts regime in which the spouts merge at a certain height. Fig. 11 compares the time averaged vertical solids velocities at three different heights obtained from TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with PIV and PEPT experiments as well as CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). At $z = 20$ mm, both TFM and CFD-DEM over-predict the solids velocities in the spouts in comparison with the experiments, however the predicted solids velocities in the spouts are lower than CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). Furthermore, as observed from the experimental profiles at $z = 50$ mm, merging of the spouts leads to a downward flow of solids in the center of the bed which can be reproduced with our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations, whereas CFD-DEM simulations of

van Buijtenen et al. (2011) do not reproduce it, indicating that their CFD-DEM simulations has not produced the solids circulation patterns between the spouts. Also, in our simulations, TFM predicts slightly higher solids velocities in the spouts than CFD-DEM. At $z = 100$ mm, CFD-DEM replicates the merging of the spouts to the quite same extent as the PIV measurements, while the TFM reproduces the lesser extent of merging matching the PEPT measurement data with higher upward solids velocities in the bed center than CFD-DEM. In terms of the downward solids velocities near the side walls, first at $z = 20$ mm profiles of our TFM, CFD-DEM and van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) CFD-DEM simulations match quite well with experiments; second, at $z = 50$ mm our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations show promising predictions with the experimental data, whereas CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) largely over-predicts the downward solids velocities; third, at $z = 100$ mm our TFM and CFD-DEM results show small discrepancies with the experiments in comparison to CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011).

From Fig. 11, it can be seen that at $z = 20$ and 50 mm increasing the rolling friction slightly affects the simulation results. Furthermore, at $z = 100$ mm using of $\mu_r = 0.125$ yields better agreement of the TFM and CFD-DEM results with the experiments near the side walls which indicates that similar to the single-spout fluidized bed, in the double-spout fluidized bed also proper resolving the particle–wall interaction results in a good agreement between the simulations and experiments. Also, the rolling friction influences the degree of the merging of the spouts in both TFM and CFD-DEM. Finally, the RMSEs of CFD-DEM and TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.125$ relative to the PIV and PEPT measurements at all height are approximately 0.02 lower than RMSEs between simulations with $\mu_r = 0.06$ and the experiments, therefore we choose to use $\mu_r = 0.125$ in the simulations of the double-spout fluidized bed.

Fig. 12 compares the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM with the experimental data of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the double-spout fluidized bed at three different heights with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125. We found out that in TFM (Schneiderbauer) simulations with $\mu_r = 0.125$ merging of the spouts does not occur (see Fig. 14). In dense regions between the spouts, a higher solids stresses are obtained from Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012), which alongside with the high solids viscosity causes to elevate frictional shear stresses which acts against the merging of the spouts. Therefore, TFM (Schneiderbauer) results are presented only at $\mu_r = 0.0$. In line with

Fig. 12. Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM with the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the double-spout fluidized bed with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125. (a) $z = 20$ mm, (b) $z = 50$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

what was discussed in the Section 4.1, excluding the rolling friction leads to higher downward solids velocities near the side walls at all heights in the double-spout fluidized bed, as well. This leads to a higher extent of deviation between the simulations and PIV and PEPT data of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) near the side walls. It can be seen that with excluding the rolling friction, at $z = 20$ and 50 mm in TFM the solids velocities in the spouts decrease while CFD-DEM results exhibit the opposite pattern. As shown in Fig. 12b, TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ shows the upward solids velocities between the spouts, indicating that it has not generated the solids circulation patterns between the spouts, whereas CFD-DEM results with $\mu_r = 0.0$ generate those. Furthermore, the solids velocities profiles at $z = 100$ mm show how excluding the rolling friction impacts the merging of the spouts differently in TFM and CFD-DEM, in TFM it causes a more pronounced spout merging akin to the PIV profiles of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011), while in CFD-DEM it results in a less pronounced merging. Eventually, comparison between TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM

simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$, indicates that at $z = 20$ and 50 mm, the solids velocities are higher in the spouts for TFM (Schneiderbauer), while at $z = 100$ mm, although both simulations show more pronounced spout merging, the upward solids velocities are lower in TFM (Schneiderbauer) simulations. Moreover, analogous to the same reason explained in Fig. 5, TFM (Schneiderbauer) predicts lower downward solids velocities than TFM simulations near the side walls.

The variation of the laterally and time averaged solids volume fraction along the height is presented in Fig. 13, where similar to the discussions of Fig. 6 an increase happens in the bottom of the bed and then the solids volume fraction starts to decrease with the height. The CFD-DEM predicts lower solids volume fraction profiles than TFM at $z=[30-260]$ mm, which can be attributed to the larger bubbles generated in CFD-DEM as can be seen in the animations of the simulations provided in the supplementary material. The CFD-DEM results also demonstrates that the solids are carried to higher elevations, which is probably a result of the eruption of the bubbles at higher elevations and this is supported by the animations available in the supplementary material. Also, as is evident in Fig. 13 TFM (Schneiderbauer) shows quite similar the time averaged solids volume fraction profile to TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$. In both TFM and CFD-DEM, excluding the rolling friction has minor effects on the time averaged solids volume fraction profiles along the bed height.

Fig. 14 shows the time averaged solids volume fraction profiles from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM in the double-spout fluidized bed. It can be seen that merging of the spouts is simulated by both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches and bubbles mainly move upward in the bed center which generates a region with lower solids volume fraction in the bed center while solids move downward in the high solids volume fraction regions at the vicinity of the side walls. As discussed also in Fig. 13 and is visible in the animations of the simulations in the supplementary material, formed bubbles in CFD-DEM are larger and also erupt at higher elevations, which forms thin layers of solids along the side walls at high elevations, but this does not occur in TFM. Additionally, excluding the rolling friction does not affect the solids volume fraction profiles in CFD-DEM significantly, but it decreases the height of the merging of the spouts in TFM. As can be seen TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ show quite similar profiles. For quantitative comparison between the time averaged profiles of solids volume fraction from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM, Fig. 15 is provided. At $z = 20$ and 50 mm, TFM exhibits slightly higher solids volume fractions near the side walls region and between the spouts and predicts lower solids volume fractions in the spouts than CFD-DEM. In both TFM and CFD-

Fig. 13. Variation of the laterally and time averaged solids volume fraction along height from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM in the double-spout fluidized bed with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 . The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

Fig. 14. The time averaged solids volume fraction profiles obtained from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM in the double-spout fluidized bed.

Fig. 15. A Comparison of the time averaged solids volume fraction extracted from TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 in the double-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 20$ mm, (b) $z = 50$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

DEM at all heights, excluding the rolling friction increases the solids volume fraction near the side walls and the bed center except for TFM results at $z = 100$ mm. In addition, TFM (Schneiderbauer) shows lower solids volume fraction in the spouts and near the side walls than TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$.

The time averaged solids axial flux profiles of the double-spout fluidized bed in Fig. 16 are calculated using Eq. (41). At $z = 20$ and 50 mm, both TFM and CFD-DEM show the upward flux of solids in the spouts with quite the same maximum solids fluxes while the downward flux is seen near the side walls and in between the spouts. There is, however, an exception at $z = 50$ mm for TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ which the upward flux of solids can be observed between the spouts due to the same reason as described in Fig. 12. Furthermore, at $z = 100$ mm the upward solids flux in the center of the bed and the downward solids flux occurs near the side wall regions. About the effect of the rolling friction, all the discussions from Fig. 12 is also valid here. The time averaged solids axial flux profiles from TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ show the same trends as the profiles of time averaged vertical solids velocities in Fig. 12.

4.3. Triple-spout fluidized bed

Following the 4.1 and 4.2, Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) inter-phase drag correlation is adopted in the triple-spout fluidized bed simulations, as well. The related spouting gas and background gas velocities from Table 7 result in multiple-interacting-spouts

regime similar to the double-spout fluidized bed. The comparison between the time averaged solids velocities from TFM and CFD-DEM with PIV and PEPT data as well as CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) are plotted in Fig. 17. At $z = 20$ mm, our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations overestimate the solids velocities in the spouts compared to the PIV and PEPT measurements but the discrepancies with the experiments are lower in comparison with CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). Further, at $z = 50$ mm the solids velocities obtained from our TFM and CFD-DEM show better consistency with the experiments than CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). At $z = 100$ mm, a less distinct merging of the spouts is predicted with our TFM and CFD-DEM models compared to PIV measurements and CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011); on the other hand, the solids velocities are in good agreement with the PEPT measurements. In general, contrary to CFD-DEM results of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011), our TFM and CFD-DEM provide preferable results especially near the side walls. Similar to the double-spout fluidized bed at $z = 20$ and 50 mm, increasing the rolling friction does not remarkably change the results. Nevertheless, at $z = 100$ mm increasing the rolling friction results in more pronounced spout merging and lower downward solids velocities near the side walls. In addition, RMSEs of CFD-DEM and TFM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.125$ relative to the PIV and PEPT measurements at all heights are approximately 0.03 lower than those for simula-

Fig. 16. The time averaged solids axial flux from TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 in the double-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 20$ mm, (b) $z = 50$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

Fig. 17. Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from TFM and CFD-DEM with the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the triple-spout fluidized bed with $\mu_r = 0.06$ and 0.125 . The solid blue line indicates the CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). (a, b) $z = 20$ mm, (c, d) $z = 50$ mm and (e, f) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width.

Fig. 18. Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM with experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in the triple-spout fluidized bed with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125. (a) $z = 20$ mm, (b) $z = 50$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

Fig. 19. Variation of the laterally and time averaged solids volume fraction along bed height from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 in the triple-spout fluidized bed. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

tions with $\mu_r = 0.06$. Therefore, as shown $\mu_r = 0.125$ yields in better agreement of TFM and CFD-DEM with the experiments and will be used in the following discussions of the triple-spout fluidized bed.

Fig. 18 compares the time averaged solids velocities profiles from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM with PIV and PEPT experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) at different heights with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125. Our TFM (Schneiderbauer) with $\mu_r = 0.125$ simulations revealed that mainly the central spout interacts with the right-hand side spout (see Fig. 20) and merging of all the spouts does not occur due to the high solids viscosity and large solids pressure from Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012). Therefore, we will only discuss the TFM (Schneiderbauer) results with $\mu_r = 0.0$ in the following. The downward solids velocities near the side walls increases in both TFM and CFD-DEM with excluding the rolling friction as discussed in the Sections 4.1 and 4.2 and it gives rise to higher deviations of TFM and CFD-DEM simulations from the experimental measurements of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). In CFD-DEM simulations, the influence of excluding the rolling friction on the solids velocities in the spouts at all heights seems insignificant, while as is obvious at $z = 50$ and 100 mm excluding the rolling friction in TFM increases the degree of the spouts merging and also at $z = 50$ mm results in the upward solids velocities between the spouts which is not consistent with the experimental data of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011). A Comparison between TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ reveals that at $z = 20$ and 50 mm both

Fig. 20. Time averaged solids volume fraction profiles obtained from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM in the triple-spout fluidized bed.

simulations predict quite similar axial solids velocities profiles with a slight difference at $z = 50$ mm. On the other hand, at $z = 100$ mm merging of the spouts is less pronounced in TFM (Schneiderbauer). In addition, due to what has been discussed in Fig. 5, the downward solids velocities near the side walls are lower in TFM (Schneiderbauer).

The variation of the laterally and time averaged solids volume fraction profiles as a function of the bed height from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM are presented in Fig. 19. The same decreasing trend of the solids volume fraction along the bed height similar to the single- and double-spout fluidized beds is observed. Similar to the double-spout fluidized bed, in general the formed bubbles size is larger in CFD-DEM except at the heights between $z=[190-320]$ mm, where TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ predicts lower solids volume fraction. These observations can be further supported by the animations of the simulations provided in the supplementary material. Also, in CFD-DEM simulations of the triple-spout fluidized bed, like the double-spout fluidized bed, the solids are entrained to higher elevations due to larger bubbles as is apparent in the animations of the simulations in the supplementary material. It can be seen that the effect of the rolling friction is negligible in CFD-DEM simulations, while as mentioned excluding the rolling friction in TFM simulations leads to larger bubbles. Moreover, the time averaged solids volume fractions of TFM (Schneiderbauer) has minor differences with TFM.

Fig. 20 exhibits the time averaged solids volume fraction profiles from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM. It can be inferred that analogous to the double-spout fluidized bed, the merging of the spouts is reproduced in our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations and bubbles mostly move in the center of the bed, causing lower solids volume fractions there. Further as discussed in Fig. 19, in CFD-DEM, the solids are entrained to higher elevations in the bed which is clear from the narrow layer of the solids close to the side walls in higher elevations. Clearly, excluding the rolling friction does not noticeably affect the solids volume fraction profiles in CFD-DEM, but the height of merging of the spouts decreases in TFM. In addition, the solids volume fraction profiles of TFM (Schneiderbauer) and TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ unveil quite similar profiles. The quantitative profiles of the solids volume fraction at three different heights are plotted in Fig. 21. It can be seen that TFM and CFD-DEM show the same behavior in all heights, lower solids volume fraction in the bed center and higher solids volume fractions between the spouts and close to the side walls. The effect of excluding the rolling friction in TFM and CFD-DEM can be explained in this way that at all heights, the solids volume fraction increases close to the side walls and only at $z = 20$ and 50 mm, the solids volume fraction increases in the spouts and decreases between the spouts. Similar to the double-spout fluidized bed profiles, TFM (Schneiderbauer) with $\mu_r = 0.0$ shows lower solids volume fractions in the spouts and near the side walls in the triple-spout fluidized bed as well.

Fig. 21. A Comparison of the time averaged solids volume fraction extracted from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 in the triple-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 20$ mm, (b) $z = 50$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

Fig. 22. The time averaged solids axial flux from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 in the triple-spout fluidized bed. (a) $z = 20$ mm, (b) $z = 50$ mm and (c) $z = 100$ mm. l is the bed width. The solid lines correspond to $\mu_r = 0.125$ and the dashed lines present $\mu_r = 0.0$.

The time averaged solids axial flux profiles calculated with Eq. (41) from TFM (Schneiderbauer), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations are presented in Fig. 22. At $z = 20$ and 50 mm, TFM and CFD-DEM simulations illustrate the upward solids fluxes in the spouts and the downward fluxes in the side wall regions and between the spouts except for TFM with $\mu_r = 0.0$ at $z = 50$ mm. At $z = 100$ mm, the upward and downward solids fluxes are apparent in the center and side walls, respectively. In general, it can be seen that by excluding the rolling friction, the upward axial solids flux in the center of the bed and the downward solids fluxes near the side walls increases. Furthermore, TFM (Schneiderbauer) with $\mu_r = 0.0$ has almost lower upward and downward solids axial fluxes in the spouts and near the side walls than TFM simulations, respectively.

5. Conclusion and outlook

In this paper, we presented a comprehensive comparison between TFM, CFD-DEM and experiments in the single-, double- and triple-spout fluidized beds. We used a TFM approach including interstitial fluid effect in the kinetic-collisional solids stresses and a $\mu(I)$ -rheology for the frictional solids stresses as well as realistic particle-wall boundary conditions of momentum transfer and the flux of pseudo-thermal energy. We also suggested a new ad hoc modification to account for the effect of particle non-sphericity in the $\mu(I)$ -rheology of frictional solids stresses. Based on the literature we discovered that including the rolling friction affects the inter-particle friction coefficient, the solids normal pressure in quasi-static regime and the maximum packing limit. We studied the impact of the frictional stresses modelling in TFM by comparing the approaches of Schneiderbauer (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and Chialvo (Chialvo et al., 2012). We observed that Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) always leads to higher stresses. Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) showed better results than Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012).

We evaluated our TFM and CFD-DEM approaches with experiments of van Buijtenen et al. (van Buijtenen et al., 2011) in single- and multiple-spout beds. Based on our results the drag model of Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2015) was used as the main inter-phase drag model in all simulations.

We observed that in the single-spout fluidized bed, TFM results with Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012), in terms of the time averaged profiles of vertical solids velocities, solids volume fractions and solids axial flux have a good agreement with CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.06 . We demonstrated that the suggested ad hoc modification for considering rolling friction in $\mu(I)$ -rheology of frictional solids stresses of TFM simulations replicates the same trend as CFD-DEM simulations. However a comparison between TFM simulations with Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) and TFM simulations with Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) revealed that TFM simulations with Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) predict lower solids velocities and axial flux in the spout as well as lower solids volume fraction was observed due to higher solids stresses predicted from this closure. Studying granular temperature in a post-processing stage, shed light on the predicted particle fluctuating energy from both approaches. It was realized that the granular temperature is higher in the spout region while it takes very small values (almost zero) in the annulus region. Also, it decreases in the spout region by moving along bed height. We discovered that TFM predicts higher granular temperature values than CFD-DEM approach in the spout region.

We showed that in the double- and triple-spout fluidized bed, TFM simulations with Chialvo frictional stress closure (Chialvo et al., 2012) reproduced the same trends as CFD-DEM simulations with $\mu_r = 0.0$ and 0.125 in terms of the time averaged profiles of vertical solids velocities, the solids volume fractions and the solids axial fluxes. While we observed the merging of the spouts in TFM simulations with Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and $\mu_r = 0.0$, it did not happen in the case of Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure (Schneiderbauer et al., 2012) and $\mu_r = 0.125$. Therefore, different frictional stress closures can lead to the different flow regimes in the multiple-spout beds. Also, it was revealed that TFM simulations of the multiple-spout fluidized beds with $\mu_r = 0.0$ do not reproduce the experimentally observed solids circulation patterns between the spouts.

In conclusion, this paper showed the importance of accounting for the particle non-sphericity, choosing suitable interphase drag correlation and applying proper sets of constitutive closures for particle-particle and particle-wall interactions in TFM simulations and their impact on conformity of TFM predictions with CFD-DEM and experiments. In addition, it was revealed that our suggested ad hoc modification for including the rolling friction in $\mu(I)$ -rheology of frictional stresses of TFM simulations can capture the hydrodynamics features of the single- and multiple-spout beds in the same way as CFD-DEM. However, as shown in the single-spout fluidized bed, inclusion of rolling friction does not affect granular temperature in CFD-DEM simulations while granular temperature profiles unveil incorrect behavior in TFM simulations with inclusion of the rolling friction. This is due to the incorrect predictions of the pseudo-thermal energy flux boundary condition while this method works perfectly with the momentum transfer boundary condition. Therefore, future modelling studies need to concentrate on the correct inclusion of the effect of the rolling friction in particle-wall boundary condition for the transfer of pseudo-thermal energy.

The presented TFM approach in this study can be applied to anticipate hydrodynamics features of the spout-fluidized beds while in case of need for particle-scale data such as particles residence time distribution, CFD-DEM simulations should be used. Also, it is possible to apply these TFM and CFD-DEM models to large scale simulations using high performance clusters. However, high performance clusters are expensive to use and they are not easy to access. There have been some efforts in the literature to tackle this problem using coarse-graining methods like spatially-averaged TFM modelling (Schneiderbauer, 2017) and coarse-grained CFD-DEM simulations (Radl and Sundaresan, 2014).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2022.118357>.

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